

Model Order Reduction Methods for Real-Time Prediction of Thermomechanical Properties of Additively Manufactured Composite Materials

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LFAM: Large Format Additive Manufacturing

LFAM machine: 1300 x 2500 x 1000 mm

CNCbárcenas DISCOVERY 3Dprinter

Composite materials

ABS + 20% CF

ABS + 20% GF

45° nozzle

Applications

Racing car aerodynamics

Wind turbine blade

Aircraft spars

Warpage!!!

Interlayer adhesion study: Set-up

Parametric study: Set-up

Time per layer
Nozzle temperature
Extrusion factor

3 parameters ^3 variables
= 27 cases

➤ LFAM process: FGF

2 Tensile testing

3 Microstructure observation

Interlayer adhesion study: Results

Mechanical results

○ ANOVA results: p-value per studied parameter

Parameter	t_L	T_N	f_e
σ_f (p-value)	0.0193	0.2872	0.0140
ϵ_f (p-value)	0.0327	0.3800	0.0000

➤ t_L and f_e significantly influential

Interlayer adhesion study: Results

Thermal results

Temperature evolution per layer along printing time

Top layer T evolution along the height of the structure

Objective

Real-time prediction with Reduced Order Models

sPGD: Sparse Proper Generalized Decomposition

The Proper Generalized Decomposition (PGD) Method

$$f(v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n) \approx \sum_{k=1}^m X_1^k(v_1) X_2^k(v_2) \dots X_n^k(v_n)$$

Separated representation: $u(\vec{x}) \approx \sum_{k=1}^m \prod_{i=1}^n F_i^{(m)}(x_i)$

Solution in Space-Time: $u(x, t) \approx \sum_{k=1}^m X^{(m)}(x) \cdot T^{(m)}(t)$

Parametric PGD: $u(x, t, \mu) \approx \sum_{k=1}^m X^{(k)}(x) \cdot T^{(k)}(t) \cdot P^{(k)}(\mu)$

The Sparse (s)PGD for a 2D case

Minimization problem solved:

$$\min \|u_m(v_1, v_2) - f(v_1, v_2)\|_2^2$$

Known function: $f(v_1, v_2)$

PGD approximation: $u_m(v_1, v_2) = \sum_{k=1}^m X_1^k(v_1) X_2^k(v_2)$

PGD function construction for n-dimensions case:

$$X_n^k(v_n) = \sum_{j=1}^{n_{cp}} N_j^k(v_n) a_{v_n, j}^k = (N_{v_n}^k)^T a_{v_n}^k$$

PGD mode: k

Shape functions: $N_j^k(v_n) \quad a_{v_n, j}^k$

sPGD Application: Mechanical

Double sPGD: Stress – Strain curve prediction

Matrices required:

- 3 parameters: $\{t_L, T_N, f_e\}$

- 50 cases:

30	230	90
30	230	100
40	240	100
50	250	100
50	250	130

- Results: 50 x (~)300 stress-strain points

Double sPGD needed

- Yellow dot: DOE: structured data cases
- Red dot: Sparse: randomly distributed data

Construction approach

- sPGD to predict stress**
 - Strain is normalized
 - Stress points interpolated
- sPGD to predict max. Strain**
 - Interpolate from the max. strain
- Combine predicted stress and strain**

sPGD Application: Thermal

Single sPGD: Thermal evolution per layer prediction

Matrices required:

- 4 parameters: $\{t_L, T_N, f_e\} + \{\text{layer}\}$

- 50 cases:
$$\begin{pmatrix} 30 & 230 & 90 \\ 30 & 230 & 100 \\ 40 & 240 & 100 \\ 50 & 250 & 100 \\ 50 & 250 & 130 \end{pmatrix} \times 133 \text{ layers}$$

- Results: T vs t_L \longrightarrow **Single sPGD needed**

Construction approach

sPGD to predict the thermal evolution per layer

- Temperature vs time where $t \in [0, t_L]$

sPGD Results: Mechanical

Stress – strain curves prediction

Note: Prior to sPGD application, noise removed by extrapolation of results from the lowest fracture point to the average.

- Shape functions: **Radial basis**
- Number of control points = **6**

Average error = 1.36%

sPGD Results: Thermal

Thermal evolution per layer curves prediction

Note: Prior to sPGD application, thermal data from the infrared data has been smoothed and cleaned to remove noise.

- Shape functions: **Radial basis**
- Number of control points = **12**

Average error = 4.96%

Conclusions

- Effective bonding between deposited layers in LFAM is achieved when the thermal gradient between adjacent layers is minimized.
- Adhesive strength is proven to be strongly correlated to thermal evolution of layers.
- Interlayer adhesion quality is greatly influenced by the distance from the bed (layer number) and 3 printing parameters:
 - Time per layer
 - Nozzle temperature
 - Extrusion factor
- The reduced order model built using the Sparse PGD method predicts in real-time:
 - Stress-strain curves with an accuracy of 98.64%
 - Thermal evolution of layers with an accuracy of 95.04%
- Feeding the ROM with sparse data increases the prediction accuracy

Future work

- Feed the ROM with real-time data to optimise the interlayer adhesion at every single layer in LFAM
- Compare solution with other MOR and machine learning techniques

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Thanks for listening!
Questions?

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